

Applying a steady state treatment to the complex one arrives at the rate law :

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]_T}{dt} = \frac{k_2 k_3 [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}'] [\text{CAT}]_T}{(k_{-2} + k_3) + k_2 [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}]}$$

This explains the fractional order with respect to substrate in the lower concentration range. At higher concentrations of the substrate the double reciprocal plots pass through origin. The reaction therefore proceeds either through a direct halogen transfer from RNHCl or through a loose complex whose stability constant is very low. Therefore the rate law assumes the form :

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]_T}{dt} = k_2' [\text{CAT}]_T [\text{substrate}]$$

The observed direct fractional dependence on acidity in case of acetoxynaphthalenes can be rationalised by invoking the protonation of the carbonyl oxygen of the acetoxy group in an equilibrium step prior to formation of the transition complex in the pre-rate determining step. Thus :

Taking the protonation equilibrium in to consideration and applying a steady state treatment to the transition complex one arrives at the rate law :

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]_T}{dt} = \frac{k_3 k_2 K [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}']_T [\text{CAT}]_T [\text{H}^+]}{(k_{-2} + k_3) + \{k_{-2} + k_3 + k_2 [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}']_T\} K [\text{H}^+]}$$

(where $R' = \text{CO.CH}_3$)

This explains the fractional dependence on the substrate and a direct fractional dependence on acidity. At lower acidity the protonation equilibria is probably not much pronounced. Hence only the unprotonated acetoxy compound reacts. The rate law would therefore become,

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]_T}{dt} = \frac{k_2 k_3 [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}']_T [\text{CAT}]_T}{(k_{-2} + k_3) + k_2 [\text{Ar}-\text{OR}']_T}$$

The product analysis has been done in case of 1-naphthol and 2-naphthol. 1-Naphthol gives 4-chloro-1-naphthol as the major product alongwith trace amounts of 2-chloroisomer. 2-Naphthol exclusively gives 1-chloro-2-naphthol.

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Studies on the Complexes of Uranium(IV), Thorium(IV) and Lanthanum(III) Acetates with *p*-Aminobenzoic acid, *m*-Aminobenzoic acid, Benzilic acid and Phthalic acid

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U(IV) and Th(IV) complexes with some chelating ligands have been synthesised recently¹⁻⁵. Under the present investigation complexes of U(IV), Th(IV) and La(III) with title ligands have been isolated and characterized on the basis of IR, electronic and magnetic susceptibility data.

Experimental

U(OAc)₄ and Th(OAc)₄ were prepared as reported in literature^{6,7}. La(OAc)₃ (BDH), *p*-aminobenzoic acid (Riedel), *m*-aminobenzoic acid (BDH), benzilic acid (E. Merck) and phthalic acid (BDH) were used as such. Absolute ethanol and dry petroleum ether (40-60°) were used.

Preparation of Complexes :

U(OAc)₄ or Th(OAc)₄ and the ligand (*p*-aminobenzoic acid or *m*-aminobenzoic acid or benzilic acid) in 1 : 4 ratio, La(OAc)₃ and the ligand in 1 : 3 ratio and U(OAc)₄ or Th(OAc)₄ and phthalic acid in 1 : 2 ratio were refluxed in ethanol, when the complex precipitated. The complexes were washed with ethanol and petroleum ether and dried in vacuum. However, benzilic acid complexes remained in solution and the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure when very fine shining crystals were left behind as residue.

The refluxing time, colour and analytical results of the complexes are given in Table 1. IR spectra of the complexes and the ligands were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 Infrared Spectrophotometer. Reflectance spectra of U(IV) complexes were recorded on a SP 700 Spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibilities of U(IV) chelates were measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance.

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEXES

Chelate No.	Formula	Colour	Refluxing period	%Found (Calcd.)	
				M	C
I	U(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	Green	30 min.	38.5 (37.9)	33.9 (34.4)
II	Th(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	White	1 hr.	37.9 (37.3)	35.1 (34.7)
III	La(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	White	1 hr.	28.8 (29.6)	40.1 (40.9)
IV	U(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	Green	30 min.	38.5 (37.9)	34.2 (34.4)
V	Th(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ COO)	White	1 hr.	42.2 (42.6)	28.2 (28.6)
VI	La(OAc) ₂ (H ₂ NC ₆ H ₄ COO)	White	1 hr.	35.0 (35.4)	34.0 (33.6)
VII	U[(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ C(OH)COO] ₂	Green	2 hrs.	20.4 (20.8)	58.0 (58.6)
VIII	Th[(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ C(OH)COO] ₂	White	2 hrs.	19.8 (20.4)	58.0 (58.9)
IX	La(OAc) ₂ [(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ C(OH)COO]	White	2 hrs.	28.4 (28.7)	44.8 (44.6)
X	U(OOCC ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	Green	30 min.	42.0 (42.1)	33.6 (33.9)
XI	Th(OOCC ₆ H ₄ COO) ₂	White	2 hrs.	42.5 (41.4)	33.9 (34.3)

Results and Discussion

While Th(IV) and La(III) complexes are stable at room temperature U(IV) complexes are unstable. The U(IV), Th(IV) and La(III) complexes do not melt but decompose at higher temperatures giving U₂O₅, ThO₂ and La₂O₃ at about 600°, 850° and 950° respectively. These complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents.

Since the position of ν(N-H) bands remains almost same in the complexes as in the ligand, it is inferred that N of the -NH₂ is not coordinated. ν_{asym}(OCO) observed at 1660 cm⁻¹ in *p*-aminobenzoic acid⁸ shifts to 1600 cm⁻¹ on complexation. ν_{sym}(OCO) occurs at 1410, 1380 and 1425 cm⁻¹ in I-III respectively. ν_{asym} and ν_{sym}(OCO) occur at 1532 and 1387 cm⁻¹ in the sodium salt⁹. IR spectra of *m*-aminobenzoic acid and chelates show that ν_{asym}(OCO) observed at 1625 cm⁻¹ for free acid moves to 1525, 1540 and 1550 cm⁻¹ in the chelates IV-VI respectively. ν_{sym}(OCO) has been observed at 1370 cm⁻¹ in chelates IV-VI. IR spectra of benzoic acid and chelates VII-IX exhibit that ν_{OH} band in benzoic acid¹⁰ occurring at 3390 cm⁻¹ appears as very broad band between 2750-2550 cm⁻¹ indicating that oxygen atom of the -OH group coordinates to the metal ions. ν_{asym}(OCO) occurring at 1725 cm⁻¹ shifts to 1650, 1670 and 1550 cm⁻¹ in VII-IX respectively and ν_{sym}(OCO) has been found at 1415, 1415 and 1440 cm⁻¹. IR spectra of phthalic acid and its chelates show that a strong band at 1690 cm⁻¹ due to ν(C=O) in the ligand shifts to 1625 and 1570 cm⁻¹ in X and XI respectively. The band at 1280 cm⁻¹ due to carboxylic group^{9,11} occurs at 1410 cm⁻¹ in X and XI. Positions of ν_{asym} and ν_{sym}(OCO) in all the complexes show that the carboxylate groups act as

bidentate. These assignments are, however, ambiguous because bands due to acetate groups also occur in the same region.

Reflectance spectra of uranium(IV) complexes (Table 2) belong to the strong intensity type on the

TABLE 2—REFLECTANCE SPECTRA OF U(IV) COMPLEXES IN nm

Term ^a	Diacetatobis (<i>p</i> -amino- benzoato) uranium(IV)	Diacetatobis (<i>m</i> -amino- benzoato) uranium(IV)	Tetrakis (benzilato) uranium(IV)	Bis(phthalato) uranium(IV)
³ F ₄	1900sh	1950w	1925w	1975m
³ H ₆	1500s	1550s	1580m	1650s
³ F ₂	1425sh	1400w	1410sh	1410sh
³ F ₄	1125vs	1150s	1100s	1175s
³ H ₆	860b	880b	840m	840b
¹ D ₂ , ¹ G ₄	—	—	780sh	780sh
¹ D ₂	680vs	680s	670vs	670vs
³ P ₁	—	540sh	540s	560s
¹ I ₆	440sh	440s	460s	490s

^a ref. 12, 13.

classification of Gans *et al.*^{12,13}. The spectra of U(IV) compounds are similar to those of other U(IV) compounds where U(IV) is eight coordinated¹⁻⁵.

The μ_{eff} of 2.42, 2.36, 2.66 and 2.35 B.M. for complexes I, IV, VII and X respectively are comparable to those reported for eight coordinated U(IV) complexes¹⁻⁵.

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Rare Earth Metal Chelates of Isoxazoles— A Potentiometric Study

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IN continuation of our earlier work¹ wherein we had reported the stability constants of 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenyl isoxazole with some bivalent metal ions, we are reporting here the stability constants of the metal chelates of 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenyl, 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-*p*-chlorophenyl and 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-*p*-methoxyphenyl isoxazole with some rare earth metal ions in 75% v/v methanol—water mixture at 35° and an ionic strength of 0.1M KNO₃ employing Calvin-Wilson method².

Experimental

The ligands used in the present investigations have been prepared by the literature method³ and their solutions are prepared in 100% methanol. The stock solutions of the alkali and the metal ions have been prepared and estimated as outlined in our earlier paper¹. A digital pH meter-Elico Model LI-120 with a combined glass and calomel electrode assembly was employed to determine the pH changes during the titrations. The following sets of solutions were prepared and titrated against 0.1M NaOH at 35°.

(i) 5 ml 0.1M HNO₃ + 4.5 ml 1M KNO₃ + 37.5 ml CH₃OH + 3 ml H₂O.

(ii) 5 ml 0.1M HNO₃ + 4.5 ml 1M KNO₃ + 5 ml 0.01M ligand in 100% methanol + 32.5 ml CH₃OH + 3 ml H₂O.

(iii) 5 ml 0.1M HNO₃ + 4.5 ml 1M KNO₃ + 5 ml 0.01M ligand in 100% methanol + 32.5 ml methanol + 0.1 ml 0.1M metal ion solution + 2.9 ml H₂O.

In all the titrations, the volume and the ionic strength is kept constant. The pH values obtained in 75% v/v of methanol—water mixture were corrected by using the method of Van Uitert and Hass⁴. The correction factor in the aquo-organic mixture is -0.12.

Results and Discussion

3-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenyl isoxazole (HL) is a weak acid due to the presence of *o*-hydroxyphenyl group at the 3 position of isoxazole. The dissociation of this ligand takes place in the following manner :

Proton ligand curves were obtained by plotting the degree of formation (\bar{n}_H) of the proton complex against pH value using the relationship derived by Irving-Rossotti⁵. The pK_a values of these ligands were obtained at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and are given in Table 1.

To study the effect of the substituent at 5-position on the dissociation of the ligand, the experiments were carried out with 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-*p*-chlorophenyl isoxazole and 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-*p*-methoxy isoxazoles. The presence of Cl in the 5 position causes the electron deficiency on the nitrogen atom as a result, the hydrogen bond present between N of isoxazole moiety and H of the OH group becomes weaker when compared to the unsubstituted compound. This helps in the easy liberation of proton in solution, thereby the pK_a of the compound decreases. While -OCH₃ being electron repelling group, it enhances the electron density on the nitrogen atom resulting in the strong hydrogen bonding thereby the pK_a of the compound increases. The formation curves were then obtained by plotting the degree of formation of the chelate (\bar{n}) against the negative logarithm of concentration of the non-protonated ligand (pL). The formation curves for these metal ligand systems obtained by plotting \bar{n} versus pL do not show significant flattening at $\bar{n}=1$ indicating that the spreading factor is low, the values of $\log K_1$ at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and $\log K_2$ at $\bar{n}=1.5$ obtained are therefore approximate. The stepwise formation constants have therefore been determined by the least square method⁶ and are listed in Table 1.